

THE MAIN FEATURES OF KINESTHETIC STYLE IN LEARNING PROCESS

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Abstract.

This article is about the main features of kinesthetic style in learning process. Characteristics of kinesthetic learners, benefits of kinesthetic learning, cognitive development, increased comprehension through physical activities, social skills development have been discussed.

Key words.

verbal, spatial-visual, aural, logical, kinesthetic, social, solitary, verbal instruction.

Different individuals may process information in a learning environment by utilizing their own preferred instructional methods. For instance, some people learn the most effectively through verbal instruction while others learn the most effectively through visual instruction. The individual's unique learning style could be the cause. Understanding your own learning style may be helpful if you are a student or professional participating in educational or development opportunities.

Learning styles are a scope of strategies through which distinct individuals learn most successfully. The idea of learning styles is based on the idea that people in groups often learn the most quickly by using different and preferred methods. A person's learning style may affect how well they absorb information, comprehend procedures, cultivate competencies, and comprehend how to apply particular skills in a real-world setting. For instance, some people might learn best by reading materials on their own, while others might do better in a setting where students work together to learn. This idea has been influenced over time by competing theories that try to explain how learning processes differ. It has been difficult for educators, academics, and theorists to agree on the most effective definition and evaluation of learning styles in light of this diversity of perspectives. As a result, even though the recommended application of this idea isn't exactly consistent, it's

important for people to know how they learn best so they can be strategic and build success while looking for training, development, and education opportunities. There are different kinds of learning styles to consider while surveying how you can most actually figure out data and foster skills. Scholars and educators have proposed a few popular learning styles in relation to this idea, including the following: verbal, spatial-visual, aural, logical, kinesthetic, social, solitary. Let's move on to the definition of a kinesthetic learner after establishing kinesthetic learning. Kinesthetic learners learn by moving their bodies and interacting with their surroundings. They need to feel or touch something in order to comprehend it better; Consequently, practical information typically prevails over theoretical ideas. Learning to skate can be a kinesthetic learning experience. You can learn how to skate by reading about it, listening to instructions, or watching videos, but deep learning happens when you actually start "doing" it.

Instead of passively listening to a lecture or watching a demonstration, a kinesthetic learner would rather engage in physical activity to learn something. As a result, practicing what you're trying to learn is the most effective method of learning. As a result, lectures may not be as effective for kinesthetic learners as classes that incorporate real-world examples.

Characters of kinesthetic learners. As a result, lectures may not be as effective for kinesthetic learners as classes that incorporate real-world examples. Instead of (only) seeing or hearing, kinesthetic learners retain information by doing. You can anticipate the best learning outcome when they engage in physical activity while learning. They will be interested in building sets from a young age; and they frequently disassemble things in an effort to learn more about them. At the point when a kid needs to contact and hold something they are keen on instead of take a gander at it, most likely they are sensation students.

The following are some typical characteristics of kinesthetic learners:

- Understand more when learning through hands-on experience
- Tend to get bored in a traditional classroom
- Learn through movement
- Enjoy sports and physical activity
- Enjoy being outside the classroom when learning (field trips, expeditions)
- Like to build things and work with their hands
- Love experimenting and testing things
- Tend to use their hands when talking
- Enjoy working with tools or instruments

- Love trying new things
- Tend to trust what they can experience or perform
- Remember spelling words better when they write them several times
- Tend to gesture while speaking
- Tend to be killed at solving puzzles and completing mazes.
- Think more clearly when able to move
- Tend to need frequent study breaks to keep focus
- Prefer making posters or charts for group projects rather than

gathering information.

A method of education known as kinesthetic learning involves students physically interacting with the content. As a result, this teaching method shares many beneficial aspects with active learning. The growth of a variety of skills, knowledge, and critical thinking abilities are among the numerous advantages of kinesthetic learning. Research led on the mind uncovers that reasoning and development are associated. Because movement increases the amount of oxygen in your blood, which aids in fueling the brain, there is a connection between cognitive and motor processes. Therefore, engaging in physical activity improves cognitive performance. Most of the time, lectures are given by the teacher, so students, especially those who use kinesthetic learning, only get basic understanding because they don't actually touch the material. In this way, to help the mental advancement of such understudies, the consideration of sensation systems and methods is essential and exceptionally useful. One of the skills you will further develop through participation in creative kinesthetic activities is communication. While participating in kinesthetic activities like group roleplaying, you can learn about teamwork and cooperation while interacting with other people. The kinesthetic approach to education is intimately connected to creativity. While partaking in various learning exercises, you as a rule need imaginative reasoning to have the option to get a handle on more from that specific movement. When learning with the kinesthetic approach, students also frequently explore their creativity by approaching the subject from a variety of angles, which in turn contributes to more robust creative thinking overall.

Through experimenting with various methods and approaches for interacting with studies, kinesthetic learning aids critical and analytical thinking skills. Instead of being passive and merely observing demonstrations or listening to theories, the kinesthetic learning style encourages students to be actively involved in the study process and discover novel approaches to problem solving. For teachers to teach effectively, it is essential to comprehend how students retain information. The

teacher can use a variety of strategies to help kinesthetic learners learn because they prefer to be physically involved in the learning process. Several instructional strategies for kinesthetic learners can be found below.

-Your lessons should include a variety of kinesthetic-friendly activities. Try to keep your lectures as brief as possible because kinesthetic learners are prone to becoming bored and unable to concentrate for extended periods of time during traditional lectures. Instead, you should try to incorporate a variety of activities like surveys, role-plays, demonstrations, dances, projects, and experiments. You can request that students work two by two or make little gatherings moving their seats to cooperate on a specific task. Presenting different exercises in the class holds sensation students back from getting exhausted while likewise assisting them with learning.

-Permit them to move. While standing during lectures may be frowned upon by some educators, did you know that doing so can be beneficial to some students? Kinesthetic learners learn more quickly when they can move around in class. Movements like standing, drawing, tapping one's leg, and others can help a physical learner focus and learn more quickly. Also, assuming you see that the sensation students in your group can't concentrate during talks, stop and have the class switch places, hop, stretch, or do something almost identical to get some energy.

-Encourage them to make the notes. Kinesthetic learners are more likely to retain information if they use a pen and paper to make their own notes, highlight sections of a book or notebook, and underline various sections. Picking either shaded pencils and highlighters is a scaled down action that requires movement and empowers sensation students who might be worn out on sitting the entire day in class.

-Educate outside. Teach outside of the classroom whenever you can or can make a connection to the lesson. You can teach students about plants by taking them outside to a park or the school backyard because students learn best from real-world examples. Instead of just reading about the plants and looking at pictures, they can feel and touch them this way. Take the understudies outside to play various games or simply notice. They will be actively learning as a benefit.

-Attempt to give a useful part to the illustrations. Since sensation students learn best by contact, at whatever point you can, offer your understudies things they can associate with actually. Puzzles, blocks, cubes, wooden letters and numbers, modeling clay, globes, maps, and other materials for drawing are among these.

For successful learning, it is essential to know your primary learning style. Kinesthetic learning was discussed in this article, one of the four main types of learning. We gave you a general understanding of this learning style by including the definition, characteristics, and advantages of kinesthetic learning. This will help you determine whether or not you are a kinesthetic learner. On the off chance that you are an educator, this article can assist you with figuring out your understudies, distinguish your sensation students in your group and utilize the system list we gave, comprising of different showing techniques for sensation students. Since, as indicated above, for a significant piece of individuals, the primary kind of discernment is visual, which most likely adds to scholastic achievement, it is important to really focus on this way of learning, for example utilize visual pictures, charts, pictures, graphs and, obviously, composed discourse. In any case, almost certainly, the vast majority of the crowd

won't get the vital data. Then again, fostering the composed language of students is vital. Consequently, when we refer to the visual method of instruction, we are referring to its mutual orientation – from the instructor to the students and from the students to the instructor.

Writing is the most difficult speech activity because it requires a lot of practice and should result in a text that readers can understand. Written speech must be more precise, clear, thoughtful, and "constructed" than oral speech because it is mediated communication. This can only be done if you are good at grammar, spelling, and punctuation. It is likewise important to have an enormous jargon, have the option to utilize an assortment of syntactic developments, know the language framework, have the option to structure the contemplations communicated in the text.

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